

Climate-Induced Displacement and the Urgent Need for Resilient Housing in Tanguar Haor, Bangladesh

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Abstract: Tanguar Haor, a critical wetland ecosystem in Bangladesh, sustains communities reliant on seasonal agriculture, fishing, and cattle grazing. However, recurring flash floods—intensified by heavy upstream runoff from India—repeatedly destroy homes and force community displacement. Findings indicate that without proper intervention, the displacement cycles will continue to erode livelihood and social structures. This study investigates the urgent need for a climate resilient housing adapted to the socio-economic and ecological context of Tanguar Haor. Through field surveys and analysis, it proposes an amphibious housing module with buoyant foundations and expandable plugins that serves both the local residents and the seasonal migrants (Bathan). Aligning architectural design with ecology and community participation, the proposed housing model demonstrates a viable pathway to reducing displacement, protecting livelihoods, and strengthening resilience in Bangladesh’s wetlands.

Keywords: Amphibious housing, Bathan, Climate-induced displacement, Resilience, Wetlands

1. BACKGROUND

Floods are becoming more frequent worldwide due to the combined effects of climate change, population growth, and human activity (Malik et al., 2020). Bangladesh, with its low-lying deltaic terrain, is especially vulnerable to annual flooding (Baky et al., 2020). Among its most flood-prone areas, Tanguar Haor—a Ramsar wetland in Sunamganj—stands out as both an ecological and socio-economic hub supporting nearly 70,000 people (Hossain et al., 2017). The haor sustains 137 fish species, 284 avian species, and livelihoods through fishing, cattle grazing, and Boro rice farming (IUCN, 2017). Seasonal migrants like the Bathan community—the nomadic cattle herders—arrive at the Tanguar Haor during the dry months to graze livestock and cultivate crops on exposed floodplains.

Environmental hazards, such as flooding, disrupt livelihoods and habitation, and triggers forced migration—a phenomenon referred to as climate-induced displacement (IPCC, 2014). With recurrent monsoon floods—worsened by upstream flows from India, road embankments, and poorly planned infrastructure (Ali, 2017; IRFC, 2022; UNICEF, 2022)—Tanguar haor communities face recurring displacements, property losses, and disrupted livelihoods.

The floods of 2017 and 2022 devastated croplands, cattle, sanitation, and housing, leaving millions stranded and deepening humanitarian crises (Abedin & Khatun, 2019; UNCT, 2022). Vulnerable groups—women, children, older adults, and people with disabilities—were at

particular risk due to inaccessible and inadequate shelters (HRW, 2023).

Despite repeated disasters by recurring monsoon floods, resilience measures remain inadequate. The existing housing of the local community, often built on fragile earthen mounds or with temporary bamboo structures, cannot withstand repeated inundation. The housing can neither accommodate the needs of seasonal migrants nor protect the vulnerable population from flood devastation. This urgent challenge sets the stage for the present study.

Figure 1. Map of Tanguar haor wetland (Source - IUCN-2015)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Climate Resilient Housing in Global Context

Global precedents demonstrate that various types of adaptive housing can mitigate risks associated with environmental disasters. In the Netherlands, amphibious homes with buoyant foundations help communities remain intact during floods (English et al., 2016). In Assam, India, elevated housing has reduced rebuilding costs by 60% in flood-prone regions (Rahman et al., 2020). Similarly, in Vietnam’s Mekong Delta, buoyant housing has lowered displacement by 70%, enabling families to stay in place during seasonal floods (Nguyen et al., 2018). The Buoyant Foundation Project retrofits existing houses with amphibious foundations that can be a cost-effective and socially acceptable alternative to an entirely new construction. This

approach offers an important lesson for the Tanguar Haor context, where resource limitations and community acceptance are critical factors in implementing flood-resilient housing (Lambeck et al., 2010). Amphibious foundations have been recognized internationally as a cost-effective and resident-friendly alternative to the permanent static elevation, particularly in areas with recurring but low-velocity flooding. Instead of remaining permanently raised, amphibious houses sit close to the ground under normal conditions and float safely above water when flooding occurs, and return to their original position as waters recede (English, 2009).

2.2 Research Gaps in Bangladesh

While Bangladesh has piloted modular and elevated housing designs, their scalability remains limited due to affordability issues and lack of technical expertise. Policy frameworks, such as the National Adaptation Plan and the UN Sustainable Development Goals, emphasize resilient infrastructure, yet they do not provide context-specific guidelines for wetland settlements (UN-Habitat, 2020). As far as we could find in the literature, such research has yet to address the Bathan community, their unique lifestyle, and relevant accommodation issues related to seasonal migration. The lifestyles and activities of Haor communities change cyclically in relation to the changing seasons. Yet very little attention has been given to how the housing of the permanent residents can remain functional throughout the year with the seasonal migrants as tenants. Seasonal migration and its integration into housing systems remain unaddressed. Moreover, research on retrofitting existing housing in Bangladesh is scarce, especially regarding strategies for long-term maintenance.

3. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The research aims to examine vulnerabilities in Tanguar Haor housing systems and proposes climate resilient housing design strategies (serving permanent residents, seasonal migrants and tourists) to mitigate displacement and sustain community livelihoods.

The objectives are:

- i) Examine the seasonal activities and living conditions of the three user groups of Tanguar Haor: permanent residents, seasonal migrants and eco-tourists.
- ii) Assess the impact of flash floods on housing and livelihoods of the local haor residents and Bathan communities.
- iii) Investigate the vulnerability of housing conditions of locals and seasonal migrants.
- iv) Propose a climate resilient housing framework for Tanguar Haor that will be adaptable to its ecological conditions, and serve all three user groups by providing a sustainable, socio-economically viable scenario for all users.

4. Methodology

This study adopted a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and spatial analysis to capture the socio-ecological realities of Tanguar Haor.

- a. Field Surveys: Field visits and direct observations documented housing typologies, flood impacts, and settlement conditions.
- b. Interviews: Conducted semi-structured interviews of 30 Bathan families and permanent residents of Tanguar Haor focusing on displacement experiences and housing needs.
- c. Secondary data: Literature review of previous research, government reports, and policy documents.
- d. GIS Mapping: Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) identified vulnerable flood-prone zones and potential elevated sites for housing intervention. Geographic Information System (GIS) tools is used to analyze potential safer spots for new housing.

5. SITE ANALYSIS: TANGUAR HAOR

Tanguar Haor covers 9,727 hectares in Sunamganj district, with seasonal transformation between dry grazing fields and monsoon floodplains. Its ecological productivity supports livelihoods but is increasingly threatened by climate-induced hazards.

Village	Monthly Income (Taka)	Main Occupation	Others
Joypur	3000-5000	Farming, Fishing, boat owning, seasonal labor	No work in monsoon. Transport is big problem
Jayosree	3000-10000	Farming, Fishing	No work in monsoon.
Lama Gao	2000-5000	Cattle Farming, Fishing, boat owning.	No work in monsoon.
Matlain	± 4500	Cattle Farming, Fishing.	No work in monsoon. 50% of the population migrate to cities for odd jobs.
Mujrai	4000-6000	Cattle Farming, Fishing, boat owning.	No work in monsoon.
Patapuka	500-1200	Fishing, restricted farming	No work in monsoon.
Nobabpur	5000-7000	Fishing, farming, day labor	No work in monsoon.

Source: Compiled from the study on DRR: A Case Study of Tanguar haor, IUCN, B. 2011

Figure 2. Current economic context based on onsite survey and study on DRR: A Case Study of Tanguar Haor, IUCN, B. 2011)

5.1 Seasonal Dynamics

Dry Season (November–April): Fertile plains for grazing and *Boro* cultivation attract seasonal Bathan herders.

Wet Season (May–October): Rising waters convert the haor into a vast inland lake, submerging settlements and displacing communities.

Figure 3. Seasonal Dynamics (1) WET SEASON (left) and (2) DRY SEASON (right)

Figure 4. Existing and potential sites identified from the contour map (prepared in QGIS 3.14)

5.2 Existing Housing Typologies

Tanguar Haor has a unique linear settlement pattern, where residents live in homesteads constructed on artificial mounds and sometimes on stilts, to avoid seasonal flooding. This traditional mound housing enables local permanent residents to continue living in the area year-round, despite the Haor submerging during the monsoon season. Such adaptation is crucial, as the entire region floods annually, leaving only the elevated land suitable for housing. This housing style is a testament to local resilience, responding effectively to seasonal changes and environmental challenges that are characteristic of the wetland ecosystems (International Union for Conservation of Nature [IUCN], 2017). The survey data shows that the current housing practices in the area primarily involve constructing homes from bamboo, thatched bamboo, reeds, wood, corrugated iron sheets, and mud. (Fig.5)

Figure 5. Existing housing typologies in the region (derived from on-site survey data)

6. FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Key Findings

- Very heavy upstream rainfall occurs in Meghalaya and Assam. Intense storms in the hills generate sudden runoff that drains rapidly into the flat basin of Tanguar Haor through transboundary rivers, triggering flash floods (Chowdhury, Shahid and Hazarika, 2019).
- The lack of safe shelters during sudden flash floods leaves families especially vulnerable, with homes and belongings often entirely lost.

- Floods disrupt livelihoods, forcing farmers and fishermen to take up day labor, coal mining, or other urban jobs as their lands are washed away.
- Housing loss often drives permanent migration to urban areas in search of safer, long-term living solutions.
- On average, households spend 30–50% of their annual income on rebuilding efforts, and this recurring loss also forces permanent migration in search of a safer and a more stable living condition.
- Survey results revealed that 80% of the households experienced home destruction and displacement during the 2022 floods.
- Stronger and more extreme rainfall (climate change) in Tanguar Haor. South Asia is experiencing increasing frequency and intensity of heavy precipitation events, particularly during the pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons, raising flash-flood risks in low-lying wetland regions such as the haors (IPCC, 2021).

6.2 Proposed Design Approach

The study proposes a modular amphibious housing system based on a buoyant foundation that enables structures to safely adapt to changing water levels. Each unit rests on concrete footings during dry periods, ensuring stability. During floods, plastic barrel pontoons beneath the floor act as floatation devices—lifting the structure as water levels rise, similar to a pontoon mechanism. This provides a crucial buffer period for inhabitants during sudden flash floods. The system is anchored with vertical guide poles on two sides, allowing vertical movement while preventing the house from drifting away from its original position. The housing system is modular. The core units can be expanded through optional plugins, such as kitchens or toilets, which the households can either add for individual use or for collective sharing. These units are arranged in expandable clusters around courtyards, creating spaces for daily use and various communal activities that may foster social cohesion. Each house includes attic spaces elevated at 2.5 meters, providing safe storage during inundation.

Figure 6. Seasonal variation of the proposed housing cluster (Left: Dry season, Right: Wet season)

Construction materials emphasize sustainability and durability, with treated bamboo and lightweight concrete forming the main structure, complemented by CI sheets and PVC for waterproofing. To ensure year-round usability, the proposed modular units are designed for seasonal adaptability. During the dry season, they can accommodate *Bathan* families migrating with their cattle, while in the wet season, when tourism in the wetlands rises, the same modules can be rented to visitors and fishermen community. This dual use not only maximizes the functionality of the housing but also integrates eco-tourism within the system, thereby enhancing livelihoods and strengthening community resilience.

Figure 7. Exploded Axonometric view of proposed module (left) ,the modulation system for multiple units (middle) Plan of a single unit module (right)

7. CONCLUSIONS

Tangour Haor’s recurring floods continue to threaten housing security, livelihoods, and the social fabric of wetland communities. This study highlights the inadequacy of existing fragile

housing systems and the urgent need for climate resilient solutions. The proposed amphibious modular housing framework, integrating buoyant foundations, modular plugins, eco-friendly materials, and inclusive design, offers a context-specific response that strengthens both resilience and livelihood opportunities. Resilient housing becomes both a physical necessity and a pathway for sustainable development and disaster risk reduction in wetland regions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author sincerely thanks thesis supervisors Dr. Asma Naz and Md. Tariquzzaman, Department of Architecture, BUET, for their guidance. Special gratitude to Md. Magfi Reza Siddique, Founder and Director of Daahuk, for his support and insights on marginalized communities, and to the *Bathan* and haor communities of Tangour Haor for sharing their lived experiences.

REFERENCES

Journal articles

- Abedin, J. and Khatun, H. (2019). Impacts of flash flood on livelihood and adaptation strategies of the haor inhabitants: A study in Tangour Haor of Sunamganj, Bangladesh. *Dhaka University Journal of Earth and Environmental Sciences*, 8(1), pp. 55–62.
- Ali, M. (2017). Impact of infrastructure on flooding in northeastern Bangladesh. *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, 10(3), pp. 402–410.
- Ali, Y. (2022). Bangladesh Haor devastating flood of April 2017: A glaring example of climate change effects. *Journal of Environmental Studies*, 10(3), pp. 45–52.
- Baky, M.A., Islam, M., Paul, S. and Hazard, R. (2020). Flood vulnerability in Bangladesh. *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, 13(2), pp. 1–15.
- Choudhury, G.A. (2016). Environmental challenges in Tangour Haor: Water pollution and sanitation issues. *International Journal of Environmental Studies*, 3(4), pp. 35–50.
- Chowdhury, M.A.I., Shahid, S. and Hazarika, M.K. (2019). Recent spatial and temporal variability of rainfall in northeastern Bangladesh. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 135(3–4), pp. 1171–1184.
- Hossain, S. et al. (2017). Impact of flash floods on agriculture in Tangour Haor Basin. *International Journal of Environmental Studies*,

3(4), pp. 42–45.

Nguyen, T. et al. (2018). Evaluating the resilience of amphibious housing in Vietnam's Mekong Delta. *Water Management Journal*, 23(9), pp. 721–738.

Rahman, M. et al. (2020). Community-engaged housing solutions for riverine flooding. *Journal of Sustainable Architecture*, 8(4), pp. 310–332.

Rahman, M.A., Bhattacharjee, M. and Rasid, M.H. (2020). Flood-resilient housing and shelter: An adaptive way for riverine Bangladesh. *Journal of Sustainable Architecture*, 8(4), pp. 333–347.

Tuli, R.D., Rashid, K.J. and Akter, T. (2024). Impact analysis of the 2022 flood event in Sylhet and Sunamganj using Google Earth Engine. *Modern Cartography Series*, 12, pp. 47–69.

Conference Proceedings

English, E. (2009, November 25–27). Amphibious foundations and the Buoyant Foundation Project: Innovative strategies for flood-resilient housing. Paper presented at the International Conference on Urban Flood Management: Road Map Towards a Flood Resilient Urban Environment, UNESCO-IHP and COST Action C22, Paris, France.

Lambeck, T., Ménard, E. and Sinclair, S. (2010). The Buoyant Foundation Project: Amphibious retrofitting of existing houses for flood resilience. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Sustainable Design and Construction*, pp. 489–496.

Book

IPCC. (2021). *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

UN-Habitat. (2020). *Sustainable housing principles for flood-prone regions*. United Nations.

Internet Document

Banglapedia. (n.d.). Bathan. In *Banglapedia: National Encyclopedia of Bangladesh* [online]. Available from:

<https://en.banglapedia.org/index.php/Bathan>

[Accessed 11 July 2025]

Human Rights Watch. (2023, June 19). *Bangladesh: Protect people most at risk during monsoon season* [online]. Available from: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2023/06/19/bangladesh-protect-people-most-risk-during-monsoon-season> [Accessed 12 September 2025].

IUCN. (2014). *Tanguar Haor: A Ramsar Site of Bangladesh*. International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN Bangladesh).

IUCN Bangladesh. (2017). *Biodiversity and ecosystem analysis of Tanguar Haor*. Dhaka: IUCN Bangladesh.

UN RC Bangladesh and UNCT Bangladesh. (2022). *2022 flash floods in north-eastern Bangladesh: Situation report*. United Nations.

Newspaper Article

The Daily Star. (2022, June 18). *Nearly three quarters of Sylhet division under water*. The Daily Star. [Accessed 5 May 2025]